

BuildingSmart Use-Case Definition – Quality Control of Installed Building Elements during Construction using Onsite Digital Twin Data

Section 1: MetaData

1.1 Identification of the document

Title:

QUALITY CONTROL OF INSTALLED BUILDING ELEMENTS DURING CONSTRUCTION USING ON-SITE DT DATA

ASHVIN: Assistants for Healthy, Safe and Productive Virtual Construction Design, Operation & Maintenance using a Digital Twin.

Short Text:

The quality management process of installed building elements during the construction stage thereby determining its conformity to the requirements specified in the contracts based on sensors and data gathering DT methods on the construction site.

Project Status:

Finished

Publisher:

N/A

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Introduction:

The current document presents a comprehensive overview and directions for utilizing the Configuration Management based framework to aid quality control in construction sites to achieve optimized productivity, resource efficiency, safety and reduced costs which are considered as the key performance indicators of the projects. Configuration Management Use Case (CMT) was deployed on several demonstration projects within Europe for quality control of installed building elements during construction using onsite Digital Twin (DT) data. The use case successfully improved the resource efficiency, productivity, safety and costs significantly at construction sites under study.

1.2 Imprint:

Project Group:

DTT, NCC

Partners:

Rehan Khan (Digital Twin Technology), NCC Sverige AB

Handling (can be edited based on preference):

N/A

Section 2: Use-Case Definition

2.1 Data Sheets & Standards

2.2 General Definition of the Use-Case

USE CASE DESCRIPTION	
Title	Quality Control of installed building elements during construction using onsite Digital Twin (DT) data.
Goal	Ensuring the quality management process of installed building elements during the construction stage thereby determining its conformity to the requirements specified in the contracts based on sensors and data gathering DT methods on the construction site.
Description	A specific framework was developed to acquire feedback from construction sites for early detection of deviation between the as-designed, and as-built products. Therewith shortening the reaction time and cost to ensure the quality requirements in the contract. This is achieved by collecting real-time data during the construction phase through IoT sensors and laser scanners and comparing it with requirements appended to BIM model.
Input Data	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. BIM model comprising of the product requirements specified assigned to the building elements during the planning/design stage. 2. Real-time data collected from sensors and scanners from the construction site with asset information of the installed building components and assists the automation of data collection from sites. 3. Configuration Management database for installed products
Sequence of actions	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Uploading the BIM Model of the desired demonstration construction site. 2. Selecting the desired elements which has to checked for quality control. 3. The panel illustrates the as-built and as-designed model comparisons to compare as-intended vs as-installed information types
Primary actors	Quality Control Team
Secondary actors	Construction Managers, construction firms and owners
Pre-conditions	Asset Information tagging – all the building assets should be physically tagged (RFID or BLE Beacon) to link BIM model and CM database.
Trigger	Quality assessment and control for commissioning of assets and buildings.
Post-conditions	Changes and relevant issues must be documented.
Frequency of use	During the installation of construction elements in the construction site and during the final inspection after the construction.
Support planned for	ASHVIN
UC Created by	DTT, NCC
Date of last update	

Figure 1 Use Case Description

✓ Aim and Scope:

The proposed use case aims to ensure that the quality management process during construction stage of infrastructure and building assets is based on and conforms to the requirements specified in the contracts with the aid of sensors and data gathering digital twin methods deployed at the construction site. The current use case presents a framework for asset information management which assists in establishing and maintaining consistency among requirements design, configured items as specified in the contract thereby ensuring quality.

✓ Objectives:

The main objective of this document is to describe the methodology developed for quality control of installed building elements during construction stage with the help of onsite digital twin data. This enables construction managers and quality control team to track as-designed/as-planned and as-built, thereby facilitating seamless commissioning of the asset.

Digital Twins as real-time feedback systems offer the possibility to link configuration information (CI) of the installed products to the digital replica of the physical asset. The current use case is developed on the premise that the use of digital technologies to integrate and manage configuration information systematically and interrelate the information between the construction phases within a comprehensive digital twin system enables a more accurate representation of the physical asset (civil infrastructure) through its entire lifecycle thereby reducing the number of changes required before commissioning the asset. The construction site progress control in the case of quality inspection and deviation check is realized by comparing the as-planned BIM model with as-built digital twin data model acquired by employing laser scanners, RFID, BLE Beacon and digital forms.

The current document also explains in detail the process models developed as part of the project, which has been validated through several demonstration projects within the EU. The referred groups for this document are construction managers, quality control team, asset owners and business partners in the construction industry, to ensure the quality of their respective assets during construction stage as per the specification in contracts.

2.3 Overall Process:

Fig 2 gives an overview for utilizing the Configuration Management Use Case for quality control of installed building elements at site. The process map given in Fig 2 gives an overview of directions for utilizing configuration management-based framework for quality assurance and management of building components installed at construction sites. It also assists in assessing the cost incurred based on the deviations from the configuration of building elements as defined in the design stage. BIM Model of the desired demonstration project is used for this use case. After creating the BIM Model of the project, building components to be checked are selected. With the help of RFID Tags, BLE Beacons and Laser Scanners in construction sites, selected building components are scanned.

Following this, the User CM database is loaded which manages the reports on inconsistencies between the as-built and as-planned models. In the next step the as-built model with information acquired from construction site by means of laser scanners or digital forms is used. The desired installed building elements can be selected from the as-built model to check its attributes, thereby verifying the quality of the installed components. The use case then assesses the cost based on deviation detected from the as-planned model and can be visualized on a dashboard. For example, during the quality check with the as-planned model, if it is determined that the installed door element is different from the one proposed from the as-planned model, the use case calculates cost implication whether it would have an increase or decrease in the proposed budget. A report on inconsistencies and impacts of proposed changes in terms of cost is presented at the end.

Figure 2 Process Map

5 Kineum office building in Sweden

The Kineum demonstration project is a high-rise building located in the city of Gothenburg, Sweden. The project started in 2019 and ended in the summer of 2022. It comprises 30,000 m², 960 – 1400 m² per floor, and 27 floors. Once completed with a height of 110 meters it is supposed to accommodate office spaces and a hotel with a nonstandard element façade with triangular glass units and a glazed roof.

As mentioned earlier, the use of the DT system to get feedback from the construction site for early detection of deviations between the as-designed and as-built products can shorten the reaction time. As-built modelling ensures the construction site is as per the requirements and is the most important source for the quality management and configuration management processes. The as-built information can be gathered from the construction site in various forms. For the Kineum site, the digital twin (DT) gathering method adopted was through a Spot robot equipped with a Leica BLK360 laser scanner to scan the progress of the site on certain areas of the building floors. The as-built information can be gathered from the construction site in various forms. Figure 3 illustrates the as-built and as-designed model comparisons of the demonstration project presented here, to compare as-intended vs as-installed information types.

Figure 3 As-designed and As-built on the ASHVIN DT platform

The resulting as-built condition of the construction site is a point cloud file which can further be made into a better 3D model. In this use case, the quality of product installations during construction is assessed whether it conforms with requirements based on the DT data gathered.

Installation of quality products as per industry standards and the client's requirements are vital for the performance of the building and are essentially dependent on the quality management plan for the specific site. The quality management for this demonstration project site was performed based on the requirements specified in the contracts, and the specifications for demonstration project are done as stipulated by **AMA**(Allmän material och byggbeskrivning).

Table 1 given below gives an overview of element door unit, the quality check of which was carried out using the Configuration Management Use Case.

Table 1: Door specification for hotel rooms

Element	Parameters	Specification
Door Unit	Door type	Internal laminated wood door, DL
	Dimensions	10mx 20m
	Sound Requirement	R w 35 dB
	Fire requirement	EL 30-SaC
	Security class	SK 3
	Locking system	Day lock

Figure 4: Selected section of the floor for demonstration

Fig.4 given above shows the selected section of the floor for demonstration of the use case of the chosen building.

For the current demonstration, a CM database is created based on actual information from the site to carry out an as-designed vs as-built evaluation. The database contains configuration information for different building elements (doors, curtain wall & pipes). The parameters to be considered are to be provided by the stakeholder for DT information gathering, in this case the main objective was aesthetics. The information from 200 rooms was gathered as intended.

Figure 5 depicts the parameter verification for one of the curtain walls. The comparison is done between what is intended at the site (as-designed) and what is installed at the site (as-built). For this use case parameters such as thermal transmittance (U-value), supply air temperature, heat exchange, and ventilation are included in the CM database. It should be noted that the application of configuration management for the quality assessment of curtain walls along with the incorporation of change management through the building's lifecycle phases is key to the building's performance.

Figure 5 Configuration information for curtain wall

Likewise for the demonstration of the CM process for the door of hotel rooms (see Figure 5) function parameters such as noise requirement, fire requirement, and security class are highly important for the quality assessment. For the sound insulation, an assessment can be carried out in a finished residential space with a mobile measuring device and then can be loaded to the CM database to check the conformity with as-planned requirements. Heat insulation properties can be assessed in a completed building by means of, for example, thermal imaging which captures the infrared radiation emitted by objects, which is directly related to their surface temperature. By detecting thermal anomalies, building owners and inspectors can target these areas for improved insulation, sealing, and overall energy efficiency. The data obtained from the site by means of thermal imaging can be loaded to the CM database and compared with the as-planning model with IFC attributes related to thermal insulation such as thermal conductivity, resistance, thermal transmittance, and specific heat capacity. Likewise, conformity of several installed building elements during the construction stage can be checked with the contract requirements upon the application of the current use case.

Figure 6 Configuration information for guest room door

2.4 Disciplines:

Please list out most favorable disciplines here:

Project Management Disciplines- Construction Management

2.5 Life Cycle Stages:

Construction stage

Section 3: Process-definition

Construction stage

Section 4: Exchange Requirements

This section gives a brief overview of the data exchange requirements for this particular use case. The configuration management use case aims to facilitate the quality check process during the construction phase based on digital twin data.

Figure 7 Exchange Requirements

In the initial project planning phase, the characteristics of the building components in relation to the various function parameters are described which are stored in the CMT database. When the BIM model is used to create a digital replica on the DT platform for the CMT use case, these data are fetched to be visualized as metadata along with their associated 3D objects. Subsequently, during the construction stage when the quality control process is done by the QA/QC team using Digital Data as means of data acquisition, they can be semi-automated process such as laser scanners along with human-controlled process such as the use of digital forms and registers to map configuration information during construction. Following which all the captured data gets uploaded to the centralized CMT database. The centralized CMT database mainly stores the as-built data from the construction site. In the CMT database it can possibly be modeled into two new instances “as-planned” and “as-procured” (later to be designated “as-built”). In the CMT use case a comparison of the two instances along with their 3D BIM models is done for digital quality management during construction. A dashboard on inconsistencies is presented between the as-planned and as-built model with cost implication of deviations from as-planned model. In the last step, CMT generates a QA/QC report as a pdf format for the outcomes to be assessed by the project management team.

Section 5: Change Log

This is a section only for changes made after publishing to the front end